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FROM TRANSGRESSION TO TRANSFORMATION OF DIASPORA IDENTITY IN JHUMPA LAHIRI'S THE LOWLAND

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Abstract

Migration is not a recent phenomenon; it has been a part of human history since time immemorial. However, with the coming of globalization by the late 1960s, the migration of people across the world has abruptly increased. Many of the educated youths and unskilled laborers due to various social, political, and economic reasons migrate from their native countries to another country. Migration not only changes the immediate physical environment but also the social and cultural environment which has a colossal impact on the identity of an individual. The interface with the new culture calls for a cultural shift that not only alters the identity of an individual but also changes the way one perceives the self. Jhumpa Lahiri's novel *The Lowland* set amidst the Maoist rebellion of Calcutta in the 1960s also highlights the issues of migration, displacement, and the consequent formation of diaspora identity. The experience of living as a migrant either temporarily or permanently in another country has facilitated diaspora writers like Jhumpa Lahiri to recognize and uncomplicated the notion of diaspora identity. Her novel *The Lowland* (2003) meticulously expresses the changing identity of the migrants. Thus, in this paper, an attempt has been made to understand the evolving nature of diaspora identity through the metaphors of transgression and transformation.

Key Words: diaspora, identity, migration, transgression, transformation

Today, diaspora has become a geographical and psychological reality that is accompanied by a series of socio-cultural transgressions as a result of the interactions with the new culture and environment. Metaphorically, the process can be correlated with transgression or alteration of not just the physical or geographical boundary but also of the social and cultural reality. Thus, it calls for traversing the political, social, and cultural milieu in which one is born. Lahiri's novel *The Lowland* narrates the intriguing attempt of its characters to transgress the native land and culture to find a home and an identity away from the home. Set in the tragic background of the Maoist rebellion of the 1960s in Calcutta, the novel predominantly covers the story of two siblings, Udayan and Subhash, and their diverse choices which not only change the course of their lives but also of the people related to them. The turbulent Naxalite uprising of West Bengal had a catastrophic impact on the lives of the people directly or indirectly

associated with it and Jhumpa Lahiri has painstakingly attempted to depict the same in her novel.

Udayan, a young educated enthusiast, who wants to alter the prevalent social structure is provoked by the maxims of the new rebellion and becomes its active member. The elder brother, Subhash on the other hand finds the rebellion bland and fruitless. He perceives the world differently. He is more concerned about change at the individual level through higher education and better job opportunity for which he chooses to migrate to the USA. Thus, the two siblings represent the two different sections of the Bengali youths of the newly independent India.

Udayan's impulsive and unreasonable nature matches with the turbulence of the revolution which compels him to secretly join the movement thereby transgressing the social and political code of the society. He is fascinated by the new movement and its ideology when he joins the radical political group in his college. Udayan's childhood experience and the prevalent exploitative system where the poor peasants were left to the mercy of their landlords and the presence of colonial supremacy in the form of institutions like Tolly Club, a symbol of the prevailing colonial supremacy which discriminated the local people and treated them as subaltern, compelled him to join the movement and become its active member. However, Udayan himself gets embroiled in the violent acts of bombing and assassination. He becomes accused of the murder of a soldier. He is hunted out of his house and miserably encountered in front of his parents. Thus, Udayan is punished for being a social rebel.

Apart from it, by choosing an independent and strong-headed girl like Gauri as his partner and eloping with her, Udayan disregards the aspirations of his parents. By denying his parents the right to choose a bride for him, he transgresses the traditional practices of the Bengal culture. As a result, Gauri always remains a stranger in the Mitra family, her condition becomes even more miserable after Udayan's death. Udayan's bold and transgressive nature is also symbolically projected through his feet imprint which he leaves on the freshly cemented room. It metaphorically represents his ubiquitous presence even after he died the lives of the Mitra's.

Subhash's, the quiet and less obvious of the Mitra brothers, bold decision to migrate to the US can be metaphorically read as a transgressive act driven by his quest to redefine his identity. Unlike Udayan, Subhash has not much expectation from the new revolution which has taken the youth of Calcutta by storm rather he chooses to continue his education and accomplish a successful career for himself. His decision to move to the US is more stirred by his desire to do something which his younger brother, Udayan could never achieve. He wants to escape the chaos spread in Calcutta and find a congenial space for himself where he can professionally bloom. The growing political activism and violence back at home disappoint him. His childhood adventure into the Tolly Club with Udayan gives him a glimpse into the luxuriant life led by the colonizers which sway him to pursue his dream of obtaining a Ph.D. degree and raising the social and economic status of his family and himself.

As brothers, Subhash and Udayan share physical resemblance but as they grow up their diverse ideological beliefs separates them. It urges Subhash to cross the border and reshape his identity away from home and his brother, Udayan. By choosing to migrate to the US, he

breaks the image of being an obedient son and brother. Subhash suffers from a sense of unexpressed contest with his brother Udayan who attempts to control or direct him due to which his presence is mostly underrated. By taking the resolution to continue his studies in the US, Subhash proclaims his destiny in his own hands. Lahiri writes:

“He’d wanted so much to leave Calcutta, not only for the sake of his education but also—he could admit this to himself now—to take a step Udayan never would. In the end, this was what had motivated him” (40).

By migrating to the US, he takes his first independent move to assert his identity. She further writes “He was proud to have come alone to America. To learn it as he once must have learned to stand and walk and speak” (38). Thus, Subhash’s decision to migrate to the US is also a transgressive or rebellious accomplishment. However, after migration, Subhash undergoes a phase of remarkable transformation or change which shapes his diaspora identity. His migration from Calcutta alienates him from his family. His longing for his family is suggestively highlighted through the geographical similarity traced by him between Rhodes Island and his native village Tollygunge in Calcutta respectively. By adapting himself to the new culture Subhash tries to mould himself in the new culture. He contravenes the teaching of his parents when he forms a close relationship with a woman named Holly. His physical closeness with a married woman Holly is also transgressive, had he been in India he would have not courted a woman like Holly. But in US, in his alienation, he gets the liberty to form a relationship with a married woman:

“Inside the room, he was able to forget about what his parents would think, and the sequences of what he was about to do. He forgot about everything other than the body of the woman in the bed with him, guiding his fingers to the hollow of her throat, over the ridge of collarbones down towards the softer skin of her breasts.” (43)

By freeing himself from the traditional mores and norms he attempts to assimilate into the new culture. When he receives a letter from Udayan stating his affair with Gauri and his elopement he is more disappointed because his younger brother has achieved a milestone much early than him. A sense of competitiveness always lingers in the mind of Subhash who wants to be away from the homely protection. He gradually explores the new land and finds new friends and companions.

By marrying Gauri, widow of his Udayan, Subhash defies his parents. His mother constantly warns him of the consequence but to rescue Gauri from the clutches of the patriarch and to give her unborn child a name and an identity.

“She’s Udayan ‘s wife, she’ll never love you, his mother had told him attempting to dissuade him. At the time he’d stood up to her, convinced it could be otherwise, and that he could make Gauri happy. He’d been determined to prove his mother wrong.” (160)

Subhash constantly supports Gauri and her individuality. He is transformed into a loving husband and caring father who accepts Bela, as his very own child.

Gauri, a graduate of philosophy from the Presidency College, Calcutta, first married to Udayan and then to Subhash represents the struggle of the Bengali women during the time of rebellion. She is representative of the woman who has to struggle hard to keep up her

individuality while bearing the strain of patriarchy. Her independent and philosophical nature attracts Udayan. As she manages to come out of the village and continue her studies even at a time when women's education was not given much importance in India. Her education and liberal thoughts enable her to make the decision for herself and choose a person like Udayan as her husband. By eloping with Udayan she transgresses the barrier of the traditional society which gives no right to the woman to choose her partner. Gauri continues to feel alienated as she is shunned by her in-laws in her own home as she has married Udayan without the consent of her in-laws. Udayan's encounter and Subhash's proposal to marry are directed to protect her. She escapes into the world of philosophy at the university and locks herself in her room. After Udayan's death she loses the only support in the family. Following it she has to bear the torture and taunt of her in-laws. She submits to them and manages to live a submissive life after Udayan's death following all the rites and rituals of being a widow. Social constraints levied on Gauri impelled Subhash to propose Gauri which helps her to transgress the limitation set by the society on her as a widow. Gauri's desire to liberate herself from the traditional bondage of being a widow enables her to accept the marriage proposal of Subhash although she could never accept Subhash as her husband.

Subhash's proposal to marry him is disdained by Gauri. Yet she accepts the proposal and migrates with Subhash to Rhodes Island. However, she has no care for Subhash and his emotions rather her sense of guilt of being a widow of Udayan and his secret accomplice in killing the police officers arouses a sense of repentance in her. Consequently, she keeps herself confined to her study and denies Subhash the right of being a husband. She even becomes negligent towards Bela and her needs as a child.

Thus, by marrying Subhash and migrating to US, Gauri on the one side attempts to run away from the crime she has witnessed. On the other side, it becomes even more settled and intense in her which takes her away from her Subhash and Bela. Gauri is left thwarted she is never at peace to herself. She transgresses the traditional limitations set for a woman in a conventional Bengali society. Migration gives her new hope and expectation to accomplish her dream of getting a degree from the university. Gauri perceives her migration as an opportunity to find a new identity that is incoherent to the new culture and identity. Unlike India, where she has to live her life according to Udayan and his parents. When she comes to the US, she gets the chance to shed the traditional custom of expectation from a family. Gauri's identity changes tremendously after her migration. It transforms her into an independent modern woman who will not be bounded by the traditional obligations rather she chooses to make the decision for herself.

Bela, the daughter of Gauri also possesses transgressive traits like her father Udayan. She championed the cause of collective well-being through her eco-friendly projects. Her wandering as a homeless wanderer sets her transgression. After, Gauri abandons her she chooses to be aloof and undisturbed by anything. She keeps herself confined and it completely changes her personality. Unlike her parents, Gauri and Subhash, she rejects the academic vocation and chooses to work as an itinerant farmer. Being traumatized by her mother's absence she prefers to live alone and tries to find meaning in life in the abode of mother nature. By becoming pregnant and giving birth to her child as a single parent she transgresses the societal norm and finds hope and happiness in it. It transforms her identity as a second-generation migrant she has no affection or attachment with anyone related to the home culture, rather she

tunes in to find an identity unconventionally. Subhash calls Bela a “nomad” (Lahiri 193), which suggests her transitional identity which is on a move. Lahiri writes

“She can’t imagine being part of a couple, or of any other family. She’s never had a romantic relationship that’s endured for any length of time” (201).

Jhumpa Lahiri in her novels has prudently handled the theme of migration and transformation of identity. Being a child of migrants, she has experienced the pangs of migration which not only calls for border crossing but also of alteration of the established social and cultural environment in which one is born. Her characters are capable of living in a world where they exist not as unified persons but as independent beings with their infinite possibilities of inventing identities through their transgressive acts which enables them to explore the unexplored selves.

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